

Modern Traditional Dilemma

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ABSTRACT

Time and Tide wait for none. And in today's scenario world is keeping space with time. If we compare the erstwhile India at the time of Independence to that at the outset of 21st Century we find considerable development in all fields, which is not confined to materialistic world only. It has affected the thinking of our people. There are daily life incidents in a family where children argue with their elders and they are restrained from doing many activities that they are fond of owing to the difference in their thinking created because of generation gap. The generation gap is the constant struggle of the parents to prevent their kids from doing things experience and wisdom. The kids on the other hand try cons to the parents that they are equipped to take control of their lives.

Indian society is known as traditional society. The old cultural traditions, customs, values were the basic features of the traditional society. But these feature are losing their importance. With the impact of west, modernization, industrialization people start adopting the features of modernity. The old generation predominantly past oriented where tradition were given more importance in the family and society. The younger generation is presumably more future oriented and more modern in comparison to the old. They believe that modern values are very useful for the society. This clash between the tradition and modernity increase the tension in the family. Generation gap can be one of the cause of this conflict.

Review Of Related Literature:-I.P. Desai (1953) in his study of high school students in Pune found severe strain on parent - ward relationship. As many as 168 respondents in his survey reported that they had wished at times to leave home of these, 117 students also gave

reason for it. About 64 percent wanted to separate because of the authoritarian, humiliating, unfair behaviour of their parents, 19 percent because of uncongenial atmosphere in the family and strain arising from it, 10 percent due to quarrels in the family and remaining 7 percent for some other reasons. The students accepted that there is generation gap prevails in family.

Hypothesis:-

It is hypothesized that there is conflict between modern traditional values and it arises tension in the family.

Methodology:-

This research was based on **primary field survey**. The field survey was conducted in lucknow city. 100 wards were selected for the study with the help of random sampling method. Two mohalla's were from each ward taken by lottery method. Two families from each mohalla's were selected by random sampling. The samples included

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400 children and parents to know their different perspectives. For this sample group, information was collected through the means of **questionnaires** and **indepth interviews** of the relevant samples .

FINDINGS

Pattern of Society in India: In the past the pattern of society was traditional. Patriach was powerful and it was he took all the decision. There was no practice of asking any question about their decision. A lack of proper understanding between parents and their children was actually causing them to distance themselves each other. But in modern time the concept of family has been changed. Parents decision regarding the life of children are not accepted by youths blindly. They oppose their parents if they think that their decisions are not right. There is friendly atmosphere in family. The practice of old - traditions prevails in the society with some modernization. Now parents are taking the decisions about their children with the advice of children. Now children want freedom but they don't want to do things, which upset their parents. They love and respect their parents. Indian society has been changing since the past but it has not lost the

Table 1

Pattern of Society In India.

	Parents		Youths	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Odd / Traditional	209	52.25	158	39.5
Modern	191	47.75	242	60.5
Total	400	100	400	100

The above table shows that 52.25% of parents think that Indian society still follow the old customs and structure while 60.5% of youths feel that the society follows the modern values. India society is changing towards the modernity. 47.75% of parents think that the pattern of society is not old 39.5% of youths believe that the pattern and structure of society still follows

the old tradition and values. There are not much changes in the Indian tradition.

The above table clearly shows that most of the parents think that the pattern of Indian society is old or traditional while the youths think vice-a-versa.

Methods to solve Clash Between tradition and modernity:

The society is not stagnant. Changes occur in every field. What was important in earlier has lost its influence in present time. Many scholars have done research on clash between tradition and modernity. Pender has rejected the tradition culture completely and believes that it slows the progress of society. For the development of society people should go with the changes of the world.

People from any age feel that their culture, value are better than the previous one. What was good for the parents does not have any impact on youths. The tradition and modernity clash exist in all over the world. Everywhere there is change in opinion, believes, perception between the younger and elder generation. This clash has not been new for society. From the early stage this was prevailed in society. The information collected from the parents and the youths about the solution of clash between the tradition and modernity can be seen in the following table

Table-2

Methods to solve Clash Between tradition and modernity:

	Parents		Youths	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
a) By rejecting the tradition	24	06	108	27
b) By rejecting the modernity	95	23.75	28	07
c) By combining the two	281	70.25	284	66
Total	400	100	400	100

The above table shows that majority of respondents both parents (70.25%) and youths (66%) feel that for solving the clash between the tradition and modernity can be solved by the combining the two. They feel that tradition and modernity both have good features. 6%

of parents reject the tradition and 23.75% of parents rejected the values of modernity. 07% of youths reject the modernity and 27% of youths reject the traditional value for solving the clash between tradition and modernity. A comparatively analysis of the table shows that in comparison to parents, the youths are more inclined towards modernity because a fairly good number of them expressed the view that clash existing between tradition and modernity can be solved by rejecting tradition or by combination of modernity and tradition.

The usefulness of old custom and traditions in modern time:-

Indian society is known for its tradition, culture, and norms. The older person believe in old traditional culture of society. Their opinion, experience and behaviour are different from the youths. The values and tradition who were the roots of society not remain any importance in present time. The youths don't want to follow caste system, untouchability, dowry, etc. which were the main feature of Indian tradition society. The people belonging to the old generation always wonder what has gone wrong with the new generation. Youths don't like the cultural traits of older time and want to follow the values and tradition, which have importance in present world. They want to go with the pace of world and they find Indian tradition as the obstacle in that situation. There is difference in the opinion of younger and elder generation towards the tradition of society. This creates generation gap in the family. Generation gap has been part of the social order for many years. This is the result of changing scenario of society from time to time. Views of the parents and their young offspring's recorded through the parents on this critical question are presented in the following table: -

Table-3
The Usefulness of Old Customs and Tradition In Modern Time.

	Parents		Youths	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Useful	317	79.25	91	22.75
Not Useful	83	20.75	309	77.25
Total	400	100	400	100

The above table shows that 79.25% of parent believe that the old customs and tradition are useful in present time. 77.25% of youths consider that in the modern time old customs have not any influence in the society. They don't want to follow the old tradition. 20.75% of parents feel that old customs and tradition not useful in modern time and 22.75% of youths feel that the old customs and tradition still have some importance in maintaining the social structure of the society.

The above table shows that the younger generation is on the opposite pole as compare to the elderly generation in regards to the attitudes towards the usefulness of old customs and tradition in the modern time.

The acceptance of modernity as a new world new:

In today's society it is quite common to hear an older person commenting on the music, clothing or life style choices of the younger generation. Times have definitely changed from when grand parents were young and even from when today's parents were a child. These difference creates a gap among the thinking of enders and youths. Today youths follow modern values, western culture, new life style, useful develop technologies etc. Parents in modern age start accepting the modernity. The rich western countries have attained a high level of modernity in their social, economic and political life. The attraction of modernity has become universal and the developing countries have also accepted the modernity in one form or the other. Youths of any country attract towards the modernity easily. They don't like the old cultural values. They want to be called modern by their friend. Modernity has impact on fooding dressing, educational system, cultural values, and family etc. People want to do whatever happens in modern developed countries. Modernity is one of the most popular concept and ideology of this age. The parents and the youths views about the desirability and agreeableness of modernity as the new world view are being presented in the following table.

Table 4
Acceptance of Modernity As A New World View:

	Parents		Youths	
	No. of Respondents	Percentage	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	163	40.75	324	81
No	237	59.25	76	19
Total	400	100	400	100

The above table clearly shows that 59.25% parents don't want to accept modernity. They believe that modern value impact negatively on society especially on youths. 81% of youths accept that modernity should be approved by parents. They think that for the progress of society and country you have to accept the modern values otherwise you can't run in the competitive world. 40.75% of parents accept the modernity and 19% of youths don't want to follow the modern values. They believe that modernity bring problems in the society.

The table reveals that in comparison to the parents a large number of young respondents have shown attitude of affection and acceptance towards modernization. This clearly shows the gap between the views of elderly and younger generation.

Suggestions

- **Communication** is the key. Open mind dialogue is desired between the youth and the parents to avoid suppression of their grouses and

misunderstandings and thereby facilitate harmonious togetherness.

- Value clarification moral education should be given to the youth.
- The parents suggested that freedom should be given to the youth with some restrictions.
- There should be pragmatic attitude among the parents towards social reality.
- There should be appreciation by the youth of valid elements in tradition.

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